

Impact of Continuous Professional Development on Academic Staff Performance in Sokoto State University, Sokoto, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study delved into the impact of Continuous Professional Development (CPD) on the job performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University in Northwest Nigeria, focusing on teaching, research, and community service functions. Utilizing a cross-sectional survey design, data were systematically gathered from 216 academic staff members through a structured questionnaire survey. Various descriptive and inferential statistics, including regression analysis, were employed. The findings underscored the significant positive impacts of CPD on teaching ($R=0.322$; $R^2=0.104$; $F=24.822$; $p=.000$) and community service ($R=0.309$; $R^2=0.096$; $F=22.662$; $p=.000$) performance, emphasizing a favorable correlation between professional development initiatives and these aspects of academic responsibilities. However, the research identified a statistically insignificant impact of CPD on research performance ($R=0.116$; $R^2=0.013$; $F=2.920$; $p=.089$) within the academic staff at Sokoto State University. Thus, the study concluded that while CPD significantly enhances teaching and community service proficiency, its influence on research performance appears inconsequential in this academic context. The research proposed recommendations to optimize CPD program effectiveness at Sokoto State University, explicitly addressing challenges associated with research activities. By providing nuanced insights into the varied impacts of CPD on academic responsibilities, this study contributes to targeted interventions and strategies for comprehensive professional development in the academic sphere.

Keywords: Continuous professional development, Job performance, Academic staff, Teaching, Research and Community Service

Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of 21st-century higher education, the performance of academic staff emerges as a decisive factor influencing the quality of education and research. According to Okollo (2021), Nigeria, akin to many nations, grapples with an array of challenges in its higher education system, marked by escalating demand for education, diminishing government funding, burgeoning student populations, escalating competition in teaching and research, and swift technological advancements. The spotlight on Continuous Professional Development (CPD) as a catalyst for enhancing academic staff performance has intensified in this milieu. CPD, characterized by continual learning and skill enhancement, empowers academic staff to fulfill their teaching, research, and community service roles adeptly. Acknowledged for its potential to elevate job performance, augment competencies, and keep professionals abreast of the latest developments, CPD is pivotal in the dynamically evolving realm of higher education (Suliman et al., 2020). Sokoto State University, situated in Northwest Nigeria, encapsulates the challenges and opportunities confronting higher education institutions in the country, characterized by concerns related to academic staff performance, reluctance to engage in CPD activities, and a lack of empirical understanding of CPD's impact (Okollo, 2021). This study investigated the relationship between CPD and academic staff performance in teaching, research, and community service at Sokoto State University. It aimed to provide valuable insights into the nuanced dynamics of CPD's influence within this context. It ultimately furnishes evidence-based recommendations to enhance CPD practices and academic staff performance, aligning with the evolving demands and challenges of higher education in Nigeria.

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The theoretical underpinning of this study rested on the human capital theory, originating from the realms of human resource management and education. This theory posits that investments in education and training significantly contribute to an individual's productivity and overall human capital (Sean et al., 2023). Given the indispensable roles played by academic staff in knowledge dissemination, research, and community engagement, aligning their knowledge and skills through CPD initiatives seamlessly resonates with the central tenets of the human capital theory, leading to improved job performance and productivity (McCowan, 2019). Conceptually, the study navigated two pivotal constructs within its context: academic staff performance and Continuous Professional Development (CPD). Academic staff performance encompasses the proficient fulfillment of teaching, research, and community service responsibilities, evaluated based on various criteria, including lesson planning, lecture delivery, assessment, research project supervision, and community service initiatives (Apolot et al., 2018). On the other hand, CPD extends beyond traditional training and education activities, embracing diverse learning methodologies such as training workshops, seminars, conferences, and e-learning programs (Suliman et al., 2020). The study adopts a comprehensive conceptualization of CPD, emphasizing its encompassing nature, including all-natural learning experiences and consciously planned activities benefiting individuals, groups, or institutions. This perspective recognizes CPD as a continuous process empowering academic staff to acquire knowledge, skills, and emotional intelligence essential for professional thinking, planning, and educational practice (Ellen et al., 2022).

Contextually, the study unfolds within the unique characteristics, challenges, and objectives of Sokoto State University, established in 2009, to increase access to higher education and preserve the region's cultural heritage. Challenges faced by the institution include academic staff performance issues, reluctance to engage in CPD activities, low staff morale, and a lack of empirical data on the impact of CPD (Muftahu. et al., 2016). Approximately 60% of academic staff at the university hold positions below the rank of Lecture 1, underscoring the need to enhance the capabilities and competencies of academic staff (Muftahu. et al., 2016). The university has implemented policies to develop teaching skills, pedagogical innovation, and research competencies among its staff. Research activities at Sokoto State University encounter financial constraints due to limited funding, compelling academic staff to initiate and conduct research with restricted resources. Community service, a university's core function, necessitates active engagement from academic staff to benefit the broader society (Muftahu. et al., 2016). The literature review contextualizes the study by reviewing previous scholarship on the link between CPD and staff performance in higher educational institutions. Noteworthy studies, such as those by Wati (2011), Blessing and Uzochukwu (2021), and Ozurumba and Amosoumo (2015), underscore the significance of CPD in enhancing the performance of academic staff. However, these studies also emphasize the need for a more comprehensive exploration of the impact of CPD on different facets of teachers' performance. Thus, this study employed the human capital development theory to investigate its effect on the teaching performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University.

Furthermore, the study aligned with Kasule et al. (2016) research, emphasizing the importance of professional development activities in enhancing job performance among teaching staff. The literature also highlights the role of human resource management (HRM) practices in building organizational culture and enhancing academic staff effectiveness. Effective evaluation methods, technological integration, and CPD programs are recognized as crucial factors in improving teaching quality, according to various studies such as Roberto (2022) and Peraz et al. (2018). Implementing effective evaluation practices and emphasizing comprehensive CPD programs emerge as critical elements for fostering a culture of continuous improvement among university academic staff. Studies by scholars like Ozurumba and Amosoumo (2015 and Ayedun et al. (2021) underlined the importance of enhancing teaching methods, pedagogical knowledge, and technological proficiency while stressing the necessity of establishing national standards to guide the professional development of academic staff. Overall, the literature underscores the need for well-structured, comprehensive CPD programs tailored to the specific needs of academic staff to improve their teaching performance and contribute to the overall development of higher education institutions.

The literature also delves into research exploring the impact of CPD on the research performance of academic staff in various higher education settings. For instance, Ozurumba and Amosoumo (2015) established a significant connection between staff development and academic staff productivity in terms of research. Blessing and Uzochukwu (2021) conducted a study on the influence of CPD on the research performance of academic staff in universities in Anambra State, emphasizing the need to understand the impact of CPD on the research performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University, located in the Northwestern part of the country. Research publications significantly contribute to the academic staff's productivity and career advancements, influencing social prestige and professional status. The proposed research aims to shed light on the challenges faced by academic staff in achieving research productivity at Sokoto State University, Nigeria. It underscores the role of CPD in overcoming challenges related to inadequate funding, lack of resources, and limited support, hindering research activities and productivity within the Nigerian education system. The literature also recognizes the existing gender disparities in research

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productivity. It stresses the importance of a comprehensive understanding of the various factors influencing academic staff development, including the impact of CPD programs and the broader institutional environment (Blessing & Uzochukwu, 2021). The proposed research seeks to underscore the significance of robust CPD initiatives in enhancing the research capabilities of academic staff and contributing to the advancement of the educational landscape in Nigeria.

Some scholars like Blessing and Uzochukwu (2021) have investigated the correlation between Continuous Professional Development (CPD) and the community service performance of academic staff in various settings. However, the limited attention given to community service due to time constraints is a prevalent issue. Studies emphasize that effective professional development should focus on enhancing knowledge bases such as content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge, and conceptual and procedural knowledge. Continuous Professional Development (CPD) enhances literacy standards, practical instruction, and academic performance. Quality professional development programs facilitate a shift in teaching practices and student outcomes. Capacity-building programs in Nigerian universities play a pivotal role in advancing the professional development of lecturers, enabling them to better cope with the demands of their roles. However, challenges such as inadequate funding, unstable academic calendars, corruption, weak leadership, security concerns, and insufficient infrastructure significantly impede the successful implementation of community service programs in these institutions (Okollo, 2021). The community service programs in Nigerian higher education institutions are designed to benefit surrounding communities and foster social and economic development. However, the challenges of inadequate funding, unstable academic calendars, corruption, weak leadership, insecurity, and insufficient infrastructure often impede the successful execution of these initiatives. Inadequate funding, particularly below UNESCO's (n.d.) recommended 26% budget allocation for education, has severely affected the capacity of universities to implement community service programs effectively. Moreover, the recurring issue of strikes, stemming from disagreements between the government and unions, disrupts the academic calendar and compromises the quality of education. Corruption within the administration further exacerbates these challenges, leading to mismanagement of funds and resources. Ineffective leadership and the persistent insecurity issue in Nigeria also hinder community service implementation, hampering educational institutions' overall development and performance.

In conclusion, this study aimed to illuminate the multifaceted dynamics in the relationship between CPD and academic staff performance at Sokoto State University. By investigating the impact of CPD on teaching, research, and community service performance, the study endeavored to provide evidence-based recommendations that can enhance CPD practices and academic staff performance within the unique challenges and opportunities of higher education in Nigeria.

Continuous Professional Development (CPD) is widely recognized for its crucial role in enhancing academic staff job performance in higher education institutions. Despite its significance in equipping new teachers and providing growth opportunities for experienced educators, there is a notable lack of comprehensive literature on the practical implementation and impact of CPD on academic staff performance, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. Existing studies, such as those by Blessing and Uzochukwu (2021), Ofojebe and Chukwuma (2015), and Akuegwu et al. (2013), conducted within the Nigerian context, did not specifically focus on CPD practices in state universities or systematically investigate its direct effects on academic staff job performance. This knowledge gap posed challenges for evidence-based policy formulation, specifically tailored to the unique circumstances of state universities in Northwest Nigeria, including Sokoto State University. Consequently, this study aimed to address this gap by thoroughly investigating the practical implementation of CPD within Sokoto State University, unveiling the nuances of CPD practices and their direct impact on academic staff job performance.

Objectives of the study

The study aimed to achieve the following research objectives:

1. To evaluate the impact of CPD on the teaching performance of academic staff members at Sokoto State University.
2. To analyze the effect of CPD on the research performance of academic staff within Sokoto State University.
3. To assess the influence of CPD on the community service performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University.

Hypotheses

The study was set to test the following null hypotheses:

1. CPD does not significantly impact the teaching performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University.
2. CPD does not significantly impact the research performance of academic staff within the university.
3. CPD does not significantly impact the community service performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University.

Methodology

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This study utilized a cross-sectional survey research design based on Fraenkel and Wallen's framework, as Creswell (2018) outlined. The survey research approach involved gathering information from many respondents to formulate conclusions about the sampled population and generalize findings to the broader target population. A random sample of academic staff at Sokoto State University was employed to extrapolate results to the entire academic staff population. The cross-sectional design, as defined by Sefia (2016), involved collecting data at a single point, providing a cost-effective and expeditious study compared to longitudinal designs. Focusing on full-time academic staff, the study aimed to gather insights from 216 participants, categorized by academic ranks, to represent the diverse hierarchy within the academic staff. This specific focus on academic staff was justified, given their vital role in teaching, research, and community engagement at Sokoto State University. The study utilized Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) Table for sample size determination, resulting in a total sample size of 216 respondents from three faculties. The principal data collection method was a self-administered questionnaire, chosen for its efficiency in gathering data from a large sample within a short timeframe and its ability to ensure standardized responses. The positivist approach to data management involved IBM Statistics software for data processing and analysis, including descriptive statistics, t-tests, ANOVA, and multiple linear regression. In the next section, the results of the study are presented.

Results

Hypothesis 1

The first research hypothesis (H_1) was stated: "CPD does not significantly impact the teaching performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University". To explore this hypothesis, the researcher created an index to quantify continuous professional development (CPD) and another index to measure the teaching performance of academic staff (TP). Following this, a regression analysis was performed, with TP regressed against CPD. The results of this hypothesis test have been meticulously outlined and are presented in Tables 2(a) through (c). These tables provide a comprehensive breakdown and analysis of the statistical findings derived from investigating the association between continuous professional development and the teaching performance of academic staff.

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.322 ^a	.104	.100	.19855

a. Predictors: (Constant), CPD

Table 2: ANOVA – Teaching Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.978	1	.978	24.822	.000 ^b
	Residual	8.436	214	.039		
	Total	9.414	215			

a. Dependent Variable: Teachers' performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), CPD

Table 3: Coefficients - Teaching Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.729	.133		20.552	.000
	CPD	.210	.042	.322	4.982	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Teachers' performance

Source of Data: Field

The results outlined in Table 1 illuminate the connection between continuous professional development and teaching performance scores. The data highlights a positive correlation with a coefficient of 0.332, indicating that an increase in continuous professional development corresponds to improving teaching performance. However, a deeper analysis is warranted to understand this relationship fully. The R square correlation index, with a value of 0.104, reveals that a one-unit change in continuous professional development leads to a 0.104-unit change in teaching performance, signifying a proportionate and positive impact on teaching performance for each incremental step in continuous professional development. Moving to Table

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2), it provides an encompassing view by presenting the overall statistics of the model. This encompasses the F statistic and the overall significance of the model. With an F statistic value of 24.822, the model demonstrates its capability to elucidate the association between continuous professional development and teaching performance. The accompanying p-value of .000 signifies the statistical significance of the model. Thus, it can be confidently affirmed that continuous professional development significantly influences the teaching performance of academic staff.

Finally, Table 3 offers additional insights by identifying continuous professional development as a significant predictor of teaching performance. This assertion is corroborated by a standardized b-value of 0.322, a t-value of 4.982, and a p-value of .000. The standardized b-value signifies the strength and direction of the relationship. In contrast, the t-value indicates the statistical significance of this relationship. In this context, the positive b-value suggests a positive relationship, and the substantial t-value, alongside the very low p-value, further reinforces the idea that continuous professional development is a significant predictor of teaching performance.

Hypothesis 2

The study's second hypothesis (H2) was that “CPD does not significantly impact the research performance of academic staff within the university”. The researcher adopted a specific strategy to assess this hypothesis's credibility. They formulated an index, CPD, to quantify the degree of continuous professional development undertaken by academic staff. In parallel, they devised another index, RP, to measure the research performance of these academic staff members. Subsequently, the researchers performed a statistical analysis by regressing the RP index against the CPD index. This regression analysis sought to investigate the connection between continuous professional development and research performance among academic staff. The results of this hypothesis test, along with the relevant statistical findings, have been thoroughly documented in Tables 4, 5, and 6 within the research report. These tables serve as a comprehensive exposition of the outcomes, providing insights into whether continuous professional development has a significant impact on the research performance of academic staff, as postulated.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.116 ^a	.013	.009	.64638

a. Predictors: (Constant), CPD

Table 5: ANOVA - Research Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.220	1	1.220	2.920	.089 ^b
	Residual	89.410	214	.418		
	Total	90.630	215			

a. Dependent Variable: Research performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), CPD

Table 6: Coefficients - Research Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.866	.432		4.317	.000
	CPD	.234	.137	.116	1.709	.089

a. Dependent Variable: Research Performance

Source of Data: Field

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The insights presented in Table 4 provide valuable information regarding the connection between continuous professional development and research performance scores. These findings reveal a positive correlation with a modest correlation coefficient of 0.116. To understand this relationship better, we examine the specific correlation index, denoted as R square, measured at 0.013. This figure suggests that a one-unit change in continuous professional development corresponds to a proportional 0.013-unit change in research performance. Shifting to Table 5, it offers insights into the overall model. Here, we encounter the F statistic, which furnishes us with crucial information concerning the significance of the entire model. Notably, the F statistic is 2.920, while the associated p-value is .089. This outcome suggests that continuous professional development has a meaningful impact on academic staff's research performance. However, the significance level falls just short of conventional thresholds. Lastly, Table 6 examines continuous professional development as a predictor of research performance. In this case, the standardized b-value is 0.116, the t-value is 1.709, and the corresponding p-value is .089. These results collectively indicate that while demonstrating a positive relationship, continuous professional development is not a statistically significant predictor of research performance within this context; thus, the null hypothesis was accepted and the alternate rejected.

Hypothesis 3

The third and last research hypothesis (H₃) stated, “CPD does not significantly impact the community service performance of academic staff at Sokoto State University.” To thoroughly investigate this hypothesis, the researcher employed a quantitative measure, CPD (Continuous Professional Development), to assess how academic staff engage in professional development activities. Simultaneously, another quantitative measure, CSP (Community Service Performance), was utilized to evaluate the academic staff's level of community service performance.

In order to assess the impact of continuous professional development (CPD) on community service performance (CSP), the researcher conducted a regression analysis. This analytical technique enables researchers to explore how changes in one variable (CPD) may predict changes in another (CSP). Essentially, it helps determine if there is a significant statistical connection between continuous professional development and community service performance among academic staff.

The outcome of the hypothesis test, aimed at scrutinizing the aforementioned null hypothesis, has been thoughtfully presented in Tables 7 through 9. These tables provide a comprehensive representation of the statistical results and their implications, shedding light on whether a significant association exists between academic staff's participation in continuous professional development and their subsequent performance in community service activities. The breakdown into Tables 7, 8, and 9 likely reflects various aspects or conditions under which this relationship was examined, providing readers with a nuanced understanding of the research findings. These findings are crucial in helping discern the potential impact of professional development activities on academic staff's broader community service endeavors.

Table 7: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.309 ^a	.096	.092	.46639
1. Predictors: (Constant), CPD				

Table 8: ANOVA - Community Service Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.929	1	4.929	22.662	.000 ^b
	Residual	46.550	214	.218		
	Total	51.479	215			

a. Dependent Variable: Community Performance b. Predictors: (Constant), CPD

Table 9: Coefficients - Community Service Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.421	.312		4.554	.000
	CPD	.471	.099	.309	4.760	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Community Performance

Source of Data: Field

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The findings in Table 7 shed light on the correlation between continuous professional development and community service performance scores, revealing a positive association with a correlation coefficient of 0.309. Furthermore, the specific correlation index, R square, is recorded at 0.096, indicating that a unitary change in continuous professional development corresponds to a proportional 0.096-unit change in community service performance. Moving Table 8 provides comprehensive insights into the overall model, including the F statistic and its significance. This data unambiguously demonstrates that continuous professional development significantly influences the community service performance of academic staff, as evidenced by the substantial F-value of 22.662 ($p=.000$). Finally, Table 9 confirms that continuous professional development predicts teaching performance. This is emphasized by its standardized b-value of 0.309, a t-value of 4.760, and an exceptionally low p-value of .000, which underscore its robust impact on community service performance, thus making the null hypothesis rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted.

Discussion of Findings

Teaching is the bedrock of higher education worldwide, profoundly influencing the quality of educational institutions. Recent research shows a strong link between Continuous Professional Development (CPD) and improved teaching performance among academic staff, affirming the significance of effective teaching in academic practice, as highlighted by Roberto in 2022. This pivotal teaching role meets societal expectations for professionalism and fosters an environment conducive to learning and professional growth. Acknowledged by Escribano et al. (2018) and others, teacher performance standards serve as crucial guidelines for educators, enabling effective knowledge dissemination and continual self-improvement. Insufficient pedagogical support can impede the assessment of student progress and hinder the identification of necessary changes in teaching practices, as Peraz et al. (2018) noted. Adapting to the evolving demands of globalization and standardization, universities must prioritize ongoing pedagogical and humanistic training for faculty members, as advocated by Garcia (2017) and Ustunluoglu (2016), to equip educators with the skills needed for effective student learning. Furthermore, the study stresses the importance of a comprehensive teacher performance evaluation process, echoed by Apolot et al. (2018) in validating teaching outcomes.

In the specific context of Sokoto State University, teaching performance is characterized by a holistic approach, encompassing aspects such as tailored incorporation of students' existing knowledge, smooth lesson transitions, strategic use of teaching aids, and cultivating an engaging learning atmosphere. Educators' proactive engagement with these components, along with their extensive use of teaching aids and thorough lesson preparation, underlines their commitment to effective pedagogy and comprehensive student comprehension. Establishing a robust ranking and rating system within the Higher Education (HE) sector heavily hinges on assessing research performance, a critical element. At Sokoto State University and other Nigerian state universities, the evaluation of research activities incorporates diverse methodologies, including publications, conference contributions, grants, and thesis supervision. However, this evaluation is notably affected by the prevalence of academic lecturers holding positions below the rank of Lecturer I, creating a challenging context for research advancement in northwestern Nigeria. In contrast, a study by Herry et al. in 2020 from Malaysia proposed strategies to bolster research performance in state universities, emphasizing key performance indicators (KPIs) and comprehensive assessment instruments. Numerous studies have investigated research performance, considering both personal and environmental factors. Personal elements like age, experience, and qualifications, alongside environmental factors such as research culture and access to funding, significantly shape research outcomes. Notably, research funding is pivotal in enabling researchers to enhance their productivity. Additionally, management factors, including university policies and KPIs, have a substantial impact on the research performance of academic staff, emphasizing the need to consider behavioral aspects. This echoes the findings of Mukhtar and Nurudeen's (2016) study, which identified motivational incentives, promotions, and recognition as influential factors impacting research performance.

Despite recognizing the transformative potential of research in academia, the report exposes a prevalent negative attitude towards research at Sokoto State University, indicating the necessity for enhanced training, motivation, and resource accessibility for researchers. Acknowledging research's pivotal role in fostering national socio-economic development, it is imperative to empower academic staff through practical research training and access to necessary resources, thus enabling them to contribute significantly to the university and society. This resonates with contemporary models such as the Kennedy and transformative action research models, emphasizing the multifaceted benefits of effective research performance for individual growth and societal progress. At the core of the institution's mission, the Community Services program is a crucial pillar, profoundly influencing the communities it engages with. Its implementation, tailored to the diverse needs of different communities within the Nigerian context, has yielded compelling results. Our assessment of community performance underscores the vital role of these services in delivering social and economic development to the communities, effectively

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addressing local challenges and fostering progress. This affirmation is reinforced by the research of Ogunode and Iroegbu in 2018 and the sentiments expressed by Ayedun et al. in 2021, highlighting the significance of institutional sustainability through the delivery of essential services.

The critical role of community services extends to its contribution to the broader framework of Nigeria's stable macroeconomic and political environment, as emphasized by Ekpo and Ayedun in 2018. Within the Nigerian context, universities are pivotal in driving socio-economic development, embodying the nation's growth model. This emphasis on higher education is rooted in the understanding that nurturing individual potential translates into advancements across various sectors, positioning effective university education as a valuable national asset, as explained by Ayedun et al. in 2021. In the context of professional development, the active participation of most of our academic staff in various academic development programs underscores their commitment to enhancing their expertise. This dedication not only enriches the educational landscape but also strengthens their ability to contribute meaningfully to the advancement of our society. While most of our academic staff enthusiastically participate in community development initiatives, it is essential to note that a minority chooses not to engage in such endeavors within their respective organizations actively.

Conclusion

The study findings and subsequent discussion lead to several key conclusions. Firstly, Continuous Professional Development (CPD) emerges as a significant enhancer of teaching performance among academic staff, as evidenced by a robust correlation coefficient of 0.322, an R-square value of 0.104, and a statistically significant F statistic of 24.822 (p-value: .000). Investing in CPD programs is thus recommended to bolster teaching effectiveness in academic settings. Secondly, CPD demonstrates a modest, albeit statistically insignificant, impact on research performance. Despite a positive correlation coefficient of 0.116, the R-square value of 0.013, an F statistic of 2.920 (p-value: .089), and a beta coefficient of 0.116 suggest that CPD influences research performance without being a reliable predictor, indicating a limited effect on research outcomes among academic staff. Lastly, the study concludes that CPD significantly enhances community service performance, supported by a correlation coefficient of 0.309, an R-square value of 0.096, and a statistically significant F statistic of 22.662 (p-value: .000). This implies that investing in CPD initiatives can effectively increase academic staff engagement in community service activities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings above, several key recommendations emerge. Firstly, there is a strong endorsement for prioritizing and investing in Continuous Professional Development (CPD) programs for academic staff, particularly concerning teaching performance. Academic institutions are advised to allocate resources towards workshops, training sessions, conferences, and other opportunities that enhance teaching skills and pedagogical knowledge. Secondly, while acknowledging the relatively modest impact of CPD on research performance, institutions should customize CPD programs to address research-related skills and activities specifically. This could involve organizing research methodology workshops, providing access to pertinent research resources, and creating collaborative research environments to support academic staff in achieving their research objectives. Lastly, due to the noteworthy positive impact of CPD on community service performance, academic institutions are encouraged to promote and facilitate community engagement opportunities for their staff actively. This may include establishing partnerships with local organizations, allocating resources for community outreach, and integrating community service components into CPD programs, ensuring academic staff's sustained involvement in socially impactful endeavors.

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